

Supporting Material for

Modelling shallow groundwater level fluctuations in very flat landscapes based on satellite data and machine learning

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Figure SM1. Correlation matrix of water table depth among monitoring wells. Color intensity represents correlation strength, with darker shades indicating stronger positive relationships.

Figure SM2. Temporal evolution of surface water area (in number of pixels) showing the data processing workflow. Gray dotted line and points: raw observations. Colored background: data quality by nodata fraction (dark green = High, <20%; light green = Good, 20-40%; orange = Fair, 40-60%; coral = Low, >60%). Blue dashed line with blue points: final gap-filled series. Blue circles: retained quality-controlled data (n = 197; 87.2%). Red circles: removed observations (n = 29; 12.8%), including unreliable data (land <50%; n = 21) and artifacts (n = 8). Artifacts detected by: extreme drops (>70%), extreme rises (>100% + >50% deviation from 3-month median), and V-shaped patterns (>100% rise after >50% drop). Gaps filled by linear interpolation.

Table SM1. Annual hydroclimatic summary for hydrological years (July–June) covering the period 2008/09–2023/24. The hydrological year is defined from July to June and is labeled as, e.g., 2008/09. Values are annual totals (PPT, PET, Balance) and annual means (WTD, SWCI, TWSA). The column “Type” classifies each hydrological year based on the 30th and 70th percentiles of annual PPT: “Dry” for PPT < 30th percentile, “Wet” for PPT > 70th percentile, and “Normal” for intermediate values. Dry years are shaded light pink and wet years light green for enhanced readability.

Hydrologic al Year	Water Balance			Indicators			Type
	PPT (mm)	PET (mm)	Balance (mm)	WTD (m)	SWCI	TWSA (cm)	
2008/2009	612	1,401	-789	-2.46	0.69	-6.56	Dry
2009/2010	917	1,319	-402	-2.73	0.85	-3.81	Normal
2010/2011	732	1,346	-614	-2.48	0.91	-4.95	Dry
2011/2012	1,106	1,583	-477	-2.37	1.81	-9.83	Wet

Hydrologic al Year	Water Balance			Indicators			Type
	PPT (mm)	PET (mm)	Balance (mm)	WTD (m)	SWCI	TWSA (cm)	
2012/2013	988	1,313	-325	-1.18	6.98	1.76	Wet
2013/2014	889	1,344	-455	-1.75	3.09	2.59	Normal
2014/2015	1,005	1,435	-431	-1.69	2.95	6.37	Wet
2015/2016	1,038	1,211	-173	-1.49	2.28	5.39	Wet
2016/2017	1,165	1,315	-150	-1.03	5.49	9.28	Wet
2017/2018	757	1,365	-608	-1.40	5.50	6.54	Normal
2018/2019	884	1,289	-405	-1.53	4.44	7.60	Normal
2019/2020	775	1,447	-672	-1.63	3.23	4.11	Normal
2020/2021	710	1,363	-654	-2.04	2.28	2.25	Dry
2021/2022	835	1,367	-532	-1.78	2.51	2.95	Normal
2022/2023	563	1,538	-975	-2.18	1.78	-2.93	Dry
2023/2024	883	1,342	-459	-3.03	0.68	-5.00	Normal

Table SM2. Quarterly summary of WTD and hydroclimatic variables for the period 2008–2024. Values represent seasonal aggregates (PPT, PET, Balance) and seasonal means (WTD, SWCI, TWSA). Seasons are defined for the Southern Hemisphere: Summer (Jan–Mar), Autumn (Apr–Jun), Winter (Jul–Sep), Spring (Oct–Dec).

Year	Season	PPT (mm)	PET (mm)	Balance (mm)	WTD (m)	SWCI	TWSA (mm)
2008	Summer (Jan–Mar)	311	432	-121	NaN	2.71	0.38
2008	Autumn (Apr–Jun)	58	166	-108	NaN	1.90	-2.51
2008	Winter (Jul–Sep)	95	204	-109	-2.19	0.84	-3.20
2008	Spring (Oct–Dec)	257	511	-254	-2.06	1.30	-4.46
2009	Summer (Jan–Mar)	168	500	-332	-2.54	0.48	-7.90
2009	Autumn (Apr–Jun)	92	187	-95	-2.97	0.16	-10.67
2009	Winter (Jul–Sep)	159	209	-50	-3.15	0.04	-9.01
2009	Spring (Oct–Dec)	343	483	-140	-3.05	0.53	-4.87
2010	Summer (Jan–Mar)	332	465	-133	-2.28	1.58	-0.31
2010	Autumn (Apr–Jun)	84	162	-78	-2.42	1.24	-1.05
2010	Winter (Jul–Sep)	110	194	-85	-2.53	1.03	-0.76
2010	Spring (Oct–Dec)	174	514	-340	-2.24	1.11	-2.59
2011	Summer (Jan–Mar)	321	474	-153	-2.59	0.36	-8.63
2011	Autumn (Apr–Jun)	127	164	-37	-2.56	1.13	-11.08
2011	Winter (Jul–Sep)	60	221	-161	-2.48	0.31	-12.30
2011	Spring (Oct–Dec)	296	519	-223	-3.01	0.79	-9.17
2012	Summer (Jan–Mar)	559	689	-129	-2.80	1.89	-10.38
2012	Autumn (Apr–Jun)	191	155	36	-1.04	5.43	-5.66

Year	Season	PPT (mm)	PET (mm)	Balance (mm)	WTD (m)	SWCI	TWSA (mm)
2012	Winter (Jul-Sep)	161	187	-25	-0.97	7.88	-1.40
2012	Spring (Oct-Dec)	-0.97	464	51	-0.72	8.51	5.26
2013	Summer (Jan-Mar)	180	492	-312	-1.34	6.44	2.44
2013	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	131	170	-39	-1.72	5.11	2.14
2013	Winter (Jul-Sep)	89	203	-114	-1.87	4.33	1.53
2013	Spring (Oct-Dec)	254	528	-274	-1.52	2.36	1.15
2014	Summer (Jan-Mar)	285	466	-181	-2.10	1.49	-0.17
2014	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	260	147	114	-1.51	4.20	6.23
2014	Winter (Jul-Sep)	119	208	-90	-1.21	4.21	7.90
2014	Spring (Oct-Dec)	285	511	-226	-1.48	3.53	8.83
2015	Summer (Jan-Mar)	220	459	-239	-2.00	2.13	4.88
2015	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	381	257	124	-1.98	2.19	4.60
2015	Winter (Jul-Sep)	120	186	-66	-1.76	1.57	3.75
2015	Spring (Oct-Dec)	314	465	-151	-1.80	1.88	2.76
2016	Summer (Jan-Mar)	395	449	-53	-1.49	2.40	6.04
2016	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	209	111	98	-0.91	3.27	8.20
2016	Winter (Jul-Sep)	102	190	-88	-0.81	4.53	8.83
2016	Spring (Oct-Dec)	401	498	-97	-0.72	5.26	9.84
2017	Summer (Jan-Mar)	403	469	-65	-1.24	6.01	7.59
2017	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	259	158	101	-1.37	6.16	10.34
2017	Winter (Jul-Sep)	150	201	-51	-0.92	8.03	NaN
2017	Spring (Oct-Dec)	215	484	-269	-0.78	7.16	NaN
2018	Summer (Jan-Mar)	179	516	-337	-1.75	3.92	NaN
2018	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	213	164	49	-2.15	2.90	6.54
2018	Winter (Jul-Sep)	144	188	-44	-1.69	4.26	7.39
2018	Spring (Oct-Dec)	300	471	-171	-1.55	3.93	9.15
2019	Summer (Jan-Mar)	287	443	-155	-1.41	4.60	7.39
2019	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	153	187	-34	-1.48	4.97	6.33
2019	Winter (Jul-Sep)	43	245	-202	-1.48	4.15	6.34
2019	Spring (Oct-Dec)	228	542	-314	-1.95	2.31	3.70
2020	Summer (Jan-Mar)	394	484	-90	-1.81	3.32	2.31
2020	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	109	175	-66	-1.29	3.14	4.07
2020	Winter (Jul-Sep)	99	198	-98	-1.52	3.82	4.13
2020	Spring (Oct-Dec)	191	521	-330	-1.76	3.36	2.41
2021	Summer (Jan-Mar)	223	465	-242	-2.32	1.21	0.69
2021	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	196	180	16	-2.55	0.74	1.75
2021	Winter (Jul-Sep)	126	218	-92	-2.30	1.53	2.84
2021	Spring (Oct-Dec)	268	495	-226	-2.18	1.75	3.69
2022	Summer (Jan-Mar)	326	472	-146	-1.46	2.77	3.17
2022	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	114	182	-68	-1.17	4.00	2.10

Year	Season	PPT (mm)	PET (mm)	Balance (mm)	WTD (m)	SWCI	TWSA (mm)
2022	Winter (Jul-Sep)	64	237	-174	-1.34	4.15	0.50
2022	Spring (Oct-Dec)	231	584	-352	-1.80	2.06	-1.39
2023	Summer (Jan-Mar)	198	527	-329	-2.41	0.72	-4.62
2023	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	70	189	-119	-3.18	0.20	-6.20
2023	Winter (Jul-Sep)	82	211	-129	-3.39	0.06	-6.15
2023	Spring (Oct-Dec)	325	498	-173	-3.32	0.18	-5.49
2024	Summer (Jan-Mar)	264	474	-210	-2.83	0.38	-5.07
2024	Autumn (Apr-Jun)	212	159	53	-2.60	2.11	-3.31
2024	Winter (Jul-Sep)	44	223	-179	-2.11	2.14	-3.28
2024	Spring (Oct-Dec)	247	524	-277	-2.26	1.13	-3.65

Figure SM3. Pearson correlation matrix among monthly hydroclimatic variables for the period 2008–2024. The matrix includes PPT, PET, and their accumulated sums over 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 months (PPT_accum_Xm, PET_accum_Xm), as well as the WTD, SWCI, and GRACE-TWSA. Correlation coefficients are calculated using pairwise complete observations. The color scale ranges from dark red (negative correlation) through white (zero) to dark blue (positive correlation).

Figure SM4. Scatterplots showing the relationship of WTD with each of the selected hydroclimatic variables. Each panel displays the relationship between WTD and one predictor variable: PPT, PET, SWCI, TWSA, and the accumulated sums of PPT and PET over 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 months (PPT_accum_Xm, PET_accum_Xm). Points represent individual monthly observations (2008 to 2024). A linear regression line (red) with a 95% confidence band (gray shaded area) is fitted to each pair, and the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) along with its associated p-value (** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, * $p < 0.05$) is displayed in the upper left corner of each facet.

Figure SM5. Comparison of observed WTD with predictions from alternative Random Forest model configurations. Panel A shows composite models combining multiple predictor groups: Full (climate + SWCI + TWSA, blue), Climate + TWSA (orange), and Climate + SWCI (green). Panel B shows simple models with fewer predictors: SWCI + TWSA (red), Climate only (purple), SWCI only (brown), and TWSA only (pink). Observed WTD is represented by the black line in both panels. All predictions are shown as dashed lines with points. See Table 2 for detailed performance metrics of each configuration.

Figure SM6 (A). Performance evaluation of combined-predictor Random Forest models for WTD prediction. Top row: Observed versus predicted WTD scatter plots with 1:1 reference line (dashed red) and regression fit (blue). Bottom row: Residual analysis showing prediction errors versus predicted values with zero-reference line. Models shown: (1) climate + SWCI + GRACE, (2) Climate + TWSA, (3) Climate + SWCI, and (4) SWCI + GRACE. Performance metrics (R^2 , RMSE, MAE) are annotated in each panel.

Figure SM6 (B). Similar to Fig. SM6(A), models shown: (5) Climate only, (6) SWCI only, and (7) GRACE only. Performance metrics (R^2 , RMSE, MAE) are annotated in each panel.

Figure SM7. Partial dependence relationships derived from SHAP analysis for top-ranking features. The plots depict how each predictor influences WTD predictions across their value ranges. Y-axis shows SHAP values (feature contribution to prediction deviation from baseline).